

Mecopteroids & Mecoptera

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Fossil Mecopteroidea

FW Cladochoristidae: *Cladochorista bryani* Riek, 1955

M. Triassic, Australia

M. Triassic

FW

FOSSIL

Tricho or Lepidoptera?? *Eocorona ianai* Tindale, 1980

M. Triassic
Australia

FOSSIL MECOPTEROIDS

Lower Permian
Obora, Moravia, FW

Note that RP and MP branches separate dichotomously and very distinctly (=proves that MA did not reduce)

Neoparachorista perkinsi Riek
Middle Triassic, Australia, FW

Neoparachorista splendida
Middle Triassic, Australia, FW
Univ. Queensland collection

FW Choristidae: *Choristis luteola*

Australian Museum, Sydney

HW Choristidae: *Choristis luteola* Australian Museum Sydney

Note distinct evidence that MA and MP are completely separate. MA fuses to RP and both sectors divide dichotomously and both branch.

HW Choristidae: *Taeniochorista*

Anal lobe starts at shallow but already expressed embayment.
 Note that it contains only AP branches, as in all blattoids, hemipteroids and endopterygotes. Note arculus is very short.

HW Eomeropidae: *Notiothauma* sp. Chile

Note that Recent plesiomorphic Mecoptera already have a short fusion arculus in their HW

HW: Mecoptera: Notiothaumidae

Mecoptera: Panorpidae, *Panorpa maculosa* HW

Note that precosto-costal proxalare (PR) is distinctly composed of two sclerites, precostal and costal, separated by a suture.

Panorpidae: *Panorpa maculosa* Hagen, 1861

The embayment shows that in the hind wing the anal lobe contains only AP veins (as in blattoids, hemipteroids and endopterygotes) while AA 1+2 is reduced and AA 3+4 becomes part of the remigium

HW Panorpidae: *Panorpa maculosa*

Hagen 1861

Mecoptera: Panorpidae

HIND WING

Panorpa sp.
classical articulation

HW Mecoptera: Panorpidae: *Panorpa maculosa*

FW Panorpididae: *Panorpa* sp.

Note: PR-PC&C (often reduced) is retained!
 PR-A&J is not fused to tergum (=plesiomorphy)
 MA and MP are very distinctly separate since basivenale (B-M), and
 MA & R fusion is shared by endopterygotes, hemipteroids and blattoids (synapomorphy)